

Intent

(What do we want to achieve with the dashboard?)

Overall Goal:
User friendly way to create and track a variety of healthy habits

The dashboard should provide actionable advice for forming and sustaining habits based on collected data that shows actionable suggestions and trends.

Technology

Constraints

Possibilities

General User Tasks

(What can users do?)

Critical Success Factors

(How do we know we achieved our intent?)

Evaluation

MVP: Data Visualization Dashboard

MVP Requirements:

Intent

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Overall Goal: User friendly way to create and track a variety of healthy habits

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Technology

Contraints

Possibilities

General User Tasks

(What can users do?)

Critical Success Factors

(How do we know we achieved our intent?)

Evaluation

User Flows

User Story Map

About Habit Apps

Positive Points

Negative Points

Room for Feature Improvement

Room for UX Improvement

Addressing Pain Points

Do our requirements fit the pain points? Do conflicts emerge?